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Assoc. Prof. Dr. Resul Öztürk

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1493-7315>

Selcuk University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Konya / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/045hgzm75>

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mehtap Öztürk

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8513-9842>

Selcuk University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Konya / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/045hgzm75>

Ph.D. Candidate Zeynep Kızıllan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9413-6253>

Selcuk University, Institute of Social Sciences, Konya / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/045hgzm75>

Exploring the Role of Green Logistics in Sustainable Performance: A Meta-Analysis with Moderator Insights

Sürdürülebilir Performansta Yeşil Lojistiğin Rolünü Keşfetmek: Moderatör Görüşleriyle Bir Meta Analiz

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between green logistics (GL) and sustainable performance (SP) through a meta-analysis that synthesizes fragmented empirical evidence. It examines the impact of GL on the core dimensions of SP: financial performance (FP), environmental performance (EP), and social performance (Soc.P.). Nineteen peer-reviewed studies were selected from major databases, including Web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCOhost, yielding 35 effect sizes based on a total sample of 7,528 observations. Effect sizes were calculated using Fisher's z transformation and analyzed with a random-effects model, while publication bias and heterogeneity were assessed using standard statistical methods. The results indicate a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between GL and overall SP ($r = 0.469$). Among the SP dimensions, EP shows the strongest association with GL ($r = 0.520$), followed by FP ($r = 0.421$), whereas Soc.P. exhibits a moderate relationship ($r = 0.353$). Analog-ANOVA analyses identify FP and EP as significant moderators, highlighting the interaction between economic and environmental outcomes in sustainability initiatives. In addition, Industrial Type, Frontier Technologies Index (FTI), Global Sustainable Competition Index (GSCI), and Country Development (CD) significantly moderate the GL-SP relationship. Overall, the study provides robust and generalizable evidence for the logistics and sustainability literature.

Keywords: Green Logistics, Sustainable Performance, Financial Performance, Environmental Performance, Social Performance, Meta-Analysis.

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, yeşil lojistik (YL) ve sürdürülebilir performans (SP) arasındaki ilişkiye ait literatürün parçalı görünümünü meta-analiz yoluyla sentezlemektedir. GL'nin SP'nin temel boyutları olan finansal performans (FP), çevresel performans (EP) ve sosyal performans (Soc.P.) üzerindeki etkisini incelemektedir. Web of Science, Scopus ve EBSCOhost gibi veritabanlarından 19 adet hakemli çalışma seçilmiş ve toplam 7.528 gözlemden oluşan bir örneklem temelinde 35 etki büyüklüğü elde edilmiştir. Etki büyüklükleri Fisher'in z dönüşümü kullanılarak hesaplanmış ve rastgele etkiler modeli ile analiz edilmiş, yayın yanlılığı ve heterojenlik ise standart istatistiksel yöntemler kullanılarak değerlendirilmiştir. Sonuçlar, GL ile genel SP arasında güçlü ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı pozitif bir ilişki olduğunu göstermektedir ($r = 0,469$). SP boyutları arasında, EP GL ile en güçlü ilişkiyi göstermektedir ($r = 0,520$), bunu FP izlemektedir ($r = 0,421$), Soc.P. ise orta derecede bir ilişki sergilemektedir ($r = 0,353$). Analog-ANOVA analizleri, FP ve EP'yi önemli moderatörler olarak tanımlayarak, sürdürülebilirlik girişimlerinde ekonomik ve çevresel sonuçlar arasındaki etkileşimi vurgulamaktadır. Ayrıca, Endüstri Türü, Öncü Teknolojiler Endeksi (FTI), Küresel Sürdürülebilir Rekabet Endeksi (GSCI) ve Ülke Kalkınması GL-SP ilişkisinde önemli ölçüde moderatör rol oynamaktadır. Genel olarak, bu çalışma lojistik ve sürdürülebilirlik literatürüne sağlam ve genelleştirilebilir kanıtlar sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeşil Lojistik, Sürdürülebilir Performans, Finansal Performans, Çevresel Performans, Sosyal Performans, Meta Analiz.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the Industrial Revolution, the global economy has grown significantly; however, this growth has come at the expense of environmental and ecosystem sustainability (Rehman et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). In the era of globalization and industrialization, pollution related to industrial development has sped up natural resource depletion and worsened climate change, biodiversity loss, and air quality degradation (Marchet et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2022). These increasing environmental issues have, in turn, put more pressure on companies to incorporate sustainability into their operations. Within this context, the logistics sector stands out, accounting for 16.2% of worldwide greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and 11.9% of transportation-related emissions (Khayyat et al., 2024). Because logistics operations are inherently dependent on fossil fuels and energy-intensive processes, they significantly contribute to global warming, carbon emissions, and broader environmental decline (Karia, 2020; Khayyat et al., 2024; Luu et al., 2023; Noorliza, 2023). In this setting, Green Logistics (GL) is seen as an approach that aims to lessen the environmental impact of logistics activities while still achieving social and economic goals. GL has evolved into a strategic method to promote sustainability across key logistics functions—including transportation, packaging, storage, and reverse logistics—to address environmental challenges (Khayyat et al., 2024; Peng et al., 2022). More generally, GL involves practices that align financial efficiency with environmental and social responsibilities. Through initiatives such as green transportation, green storage, green packaging, carbon emission management, reverse logistics, and digitalization, GL can reduce carbon emissions and operational costs simultaneously, while enhancing corporate reputation and fostering sustainable competitive advantages (Baah et al., 2021; Wang, 2019).

The strategic importance of GL has grown as companies increasingly aim to align with Sustainable Development Goal 12 (SDG 12), which highlights responsible consumption and production through actions like waste reduction, limiting harmful emissions, and promoting sustainable procurement (Khayyat et al., 2024). This trend aligns with a broader movement toward resource-based approaches to sustainability, especially the Natural Resource-Based Theory (NRBT). NRBT suggests that organizations can gain a competitive advantage and improve performance by effectively managing and utilizing natural resources as part of stronger sustainability initiatives (Hart, 1995). Building on this perspective, the present study demonstrates how logistics companies can strategically leverage environmental and resource-related capabilities to promote sustainable practices and support long-term success.

Accordingly, firms implement GL not only to meet stakeholder expectations and regulatory requirements but also to achieve performance gains (da Silva et al., 2023; Odock et al., 2024). However, prior research on the relationship between GL and SP remains mixed and, at times, contradictory. While some studies report positive associations, others find weak or non-significant effects or focus only on one dimension of performance (e.g., financial or environmental outcomes) rather than a broader perspective (Odock et al., 2024; Pullman et al., 2009). Additionally, this study examines moderator variables that may influence the GL–SP relationship—namely, methodological effects; industrial type, sample size, contextual effects; FTI, GSCI, and economic effects; and CD—thus generating insights relevant to both scholarship and practice. Therefore, using a meta-analytic approach, this study systematically synthesizes empirical evidence from the literature, assesses the factors that may affect this relationship more comprehensively, and offers findings with greater generalizability. Finally, recommendations are provided for researchers, practitioners, and future studies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Green Logistics

Since the early 1990s, the logistics sector has shown increasing interest in environmental practices and related initiatives (Noorliza, 2023). Among the sector's impacts, carbon dioxide emissions from freight vehicles and maritime shipping are particularly problematic because of their contribution to ecological damage (Trivellas et al., 2020). Logistics is widely viewed as a major source of environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions—especially CO₂—while also serving as a key driver of global economic activity by enabling the movement of goods and people. From an NRBT perspective, this dual role highlights how logistics operations could be organized to use environmental resources more efficiently and how conservation efforts might also provide strategic benefits (Barney, 1991). At the same time, the growth of the logistics industry has greatly influenced the global economy and has helped sustain rapid development (Zhang et al., 2023). However, the rise of online shopping and home delivery has increased transportation intensity and traffic volumes, putting additional pressure on logistics systems. As demand has increased, the sector's environmental footprint has expanded, causing significant environmental

degradation (Karia, 2020). Because logistics and transportation consume substantial fuel, they produce high levels of carbon emissions, worsening climate change concerns (Lyulyov et al., 2023). Transportation-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions—particularly those from freight—make up 15% of total GHG emissions, with carbon dioxide accounting for 23%. CO₂ emissions rose by 40% between 1990 and 2007 and are expected to grow another 45% by 2030 (Karia, 2020). For these reasons, integrating environmental considerations into logistics has become increasingly urgent (Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020).

NRBT further explains how firms can attain a competitive advantage by managing and deploying environmental resources more effectively. In the logistics context, firms may reduce both ecological impacts and costs by using environmental resources more efficiently (Hart, 1995). Accordingly, sustainable competitive advantage in the sector becomes more attainable when natural resources are used responsibly, and green logistics practices can serve as a key mechanism for achieving this. In particular, expanding sustainable transportation alternatives, adopting more efficient distribution approaches, and implementing systematic carbon-reduction strategies represent important pathways to reducing the environmental impact of logistics activities (McKinnon, 2010).

Logistics is increasingly seen as a significant environmental issue, especially in developing countries where its ecological impact has gained broader international attention (Baah et al., 2020). In supply chain management, logistics remains crucial for meeting consumer needs; therefore, resource management—one of NRBT's core principles—provides a foundation for organizing logistics activities in a more environmentally responsible way. This broad scope can include, for example, coordinating control systems, ensuring comprehensive data storage, and facilitating the smooth movement of products from origin to final user. In practice, logistics typically encompasses core functions such as procurement, distribution, maintenance, inventory management, product development, and finance. Conversely, marketing activities—despite their relevance to supply chain outcomes—are often considered outside this scope. Recently, GL has gained attention by highlighting sustainability across supply chain activities, including responsible management of production processes, distribution methods, packaging choices, waste handling, and promoting energy-efficient, environmentally friendly transportation options. Additionally, GL stresses environmental management and social responsibility as essential parts of logistics operations (Khayyat et al., 2024).

Although GL began to develop in the early 1990s as a response to environmental pressures, it has become a key focus area due to the rapid increase in logistics demand and growing sustainability requirements (Tran, 2024). NRBT sees environmental sustainability as a potential source of competitive advantage, indicating that logistics companies can achieve long-term superiority by effectively managing natural resources (Hart, 1995). Today, environmental considerations are integrated into logistics strategies, and terms like green logistics and eco-friendly logistics are increasingly used to describe this focus (Wang, 2019). Operationally, GL initiatives generally aim to cut carbon emissions, use environmentally friendly containers and packaging, promote green transportation, and reduce the supply chain's overall environmental impact (Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023). Therefore, GL seeks to minimize the ecological footprint of logistics activities, lower energy use and waste, enhance product and brand value, boost operational efficiency, and reduce costs through more efficient energy use. In doing so, GL encourages eco-friendly containers and sustainable packaging while aiming to cut emissions, waste, and environmental impacts across the supply chain (Afum et al., 2022; Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020; Khayyat et al., 2024).

In conclusion, NRBT implies that integrating sustainable practices into logistics is essential for both mitigating environmental impacts and developing a competitive advantage. By pursuing environmental sustainability strategies, logistics firms can use resources more efficiently and reduce long-term costs through greener approaches. This supports the sector's future development while also contributing to efforts to address global environmental challenges (Karia, 2020).

2.2. Green Logistics and Sustainable Performance

Economic development and environmental protection are widely recognized as key national goals today, and in many cases, they overlap. However, economic growth often boosts the demand for goods and services, which can increase environmental pressures and cause degradation (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010; Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023). In this context, sustainability has become increasingly central to firms' strategic focus since Hart's (1995) introduction of the concept. At the same time, as Iacovidou et al. (2021) note, many organizations still struggle to develop effective strategies for improving environmental efficiency.

These difficulties frequently arise from operational, financial, and environmental constraints that firms face when trying to implement sustainability practices. NRBT argues that firms can gain a competitive advantage by efficiently using scarce natural resources (Barney, 1991). This approach guides organizations toward strategies that simultaneously enhance economic results and environmental performance through the sustainable use of resources.

GL practices become especially important for enhancing sustainable performance when they are embedded within organizational operating systems. GL refers to a set of strategies aimed at reducing environmental impacts while also increasing social welfare (Afum et al., 2022; Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020; Hussain, 2018). In practice, logistics processes are increasingly being redesigned to improve supply chain efficiency and promote environmental sustainability. The literature also indicates that green logistics applications include a wide range of methods, such as information collection and dissemination, freight transportation, inventory management, and material handling (Centobelli et al., 2018). From an NRBT perspective, these practices can help firms use natural resources more efficiently, thereby strengthening their competitive advantage through GL-driven improvements.

Studies examining the GL–SP relationship commonly suggest that performance benefits are associated with efficiency gains from cleaner, more environmentally responsible logistics practices (Li et al., 2021). McKinnon et al. (2015) and McKinnon (2010) also underscore the role of GL in advancing environmental sustainability. In particular, practices such as eco-friendly packaging, recycling, renewable energy use, and green diesel fuels are frequently highlighted as mechanisms to improve sustainable performance. In line with this, Hart's (1995) Resource-Based Theory emphasizes that firms should utilize environmental resources efficiently to achieve competitive advantage. Accordingly, integrating GL into business strategies is commonly regarded as a necessary step toward these objectives.

This study examines the relationship between GL and SP through a meta-analysis approach. Prior studies show that adopting green practices can enhance competitiveness in the logistics industry while also improving environmental results (Li et al., 2021; Noorliza, 2023). Empirical research on the link between green logistics practices and firm performance further reveals that green logistics strategies positively impact sustainable business success and contribute to overall organizational achievement (Odock et al., 2024). Evidence from Karia also indicates that GL practices are a key driver of sustainable development (Karia, 2020). Based on this rationale, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₁: The relationship between GL and SP is positive and significant.

Adopting environmentally friendly practices not only yields environmental benefits but may also generate operational efficiencies and cost savings (Odock et al., 2024). In this regard, GL practices can improve operational processes and create reinforcing cycles that enhance firm outcomes (Chatzoudes et al., 2024). The view that GL contributes to improved financial performance is also well established in the literature (Agyabeng-Mensah, Ahenkorah, et al., 2020). Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₂: The relationship between GL and FP is positive and significant.

The influence of GL practices on environmental performance has also garnered significant attention. Evidence reported by Afum et al. (Afum et al., 2022) and Agyabeng-Mensah et al. (Agyabeng-Mensah, Ahenkorah, et al., 2020) shows that green logistics practices enhance environmental performance and that environmentally focused logistics practices deliver clear environmental benefits for organizations. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₃: The relationship between GL and EP is positive and significant.

Finally, GL is frequently discussed as a pathway for strengthening firms' social responsibility outcomes while also supporting environmental performance improvements (Sharma et al., 2023). Beyond its contribution to environmental sustainability, GL may also enhance social performance. In this context, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₄: The relationship between GL and Soc.P. is positive and significant.

2.3. Moderator Effects

Moderator variables in meta-analysis differ from traditional moderators in primary studies because they are often derived from control variables reported in empirical research. Consequently, in correlational meta-analysis, a moderator is usually seen as a third variable that affects the zero-order relationship between the independent and dependent variables (Geng et al., 2017; Hunter, 2004). Similarly, Koeske (Koeske, 1992)

described moderators as “third variables” that influence either the strength or the nature of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In this study, moderator variables are categorized into three groups: methodological, economic, and contextual. Past research has highlighted several methodological features—such as sample size and industry type—that may impact the sustainability of GL practices' performance implications (Geng et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2008).

Methodological decisions can alter the strength of observed effect sizes (Wu et al., 2012; Wu, 2013). Sample size is particularly important because smaller samples tend to be more homogeneous and may therefore yield more precise estimates of effect sizes (Fang & Zhang, 2018; Fern & Monroe, 1996). Given these properties, the sample size was included in this meta-analysis to account for systematic differences across studies in the GL–SP relationship, especially since primary studies typically report separate effect sizes and treat such variables differently. Industry type was also included because many cross-sectional studies draw evidence from multiple sectors rather than a single industry. As Del Río et al. (2011) noted, multi-industry data often exhibit greater heterogeneity than single-industry data. For this reason, industry type was incorporated to test whether it moderates the relationship between YL and SP.

Country Development (low-income and high-income) was examined as an economic moderator (Bitencourt et al., 2020). The corresponding coding relied on the United Nations classification (see Appendix A1). Countries differ in institutional infrastructure, cultural characteristics, and educational structures, which together constitute the contextual environment of developed versus developing settings (Wiengarten et al., 2019). In developing economies, interpersonal ties and social networks may be especially influential in fostering cooperation, as illustrated in China. Such differences across economic regions can also shape supply chain structures and logistics activities (Wang et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2010). Therefore, given the expectation that the Country Development YL–SP relationship may vary across these settings, this moderator was included in the analysis.

Two contextual moderators were also considered: the FTI and the GSC. The FTI includes a broad set of technologies—such as IoT, Concentrated Solar Power, Blockchain, Nanotechnology, Big Data, 5G, Biofuels, Electric Vehicles, Gene Editing, Robotics, Drone Technology, 3D Printing, Wind Energy, Biogas and Biomass, Green Hydrogen, Solar PV, AI—and classifies countries into four groups: high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low (UNCTAD, 2023). The FTI was incorporated because higher frontier-technology capacity was expected to facilitate YL applications and support the achievement of YL objectives, thereby potentially shaping SP outcomes. The second contextual indicator, the GSCI, was also included. GSCI assesses countries' global sustainable competitiveness using 111 SolAbility metrics, organized under six pillars: (1) resource efficiency and intensity, (2) natural capital, (3) governance efficiency, (4) intellectual capital, (5) economic sustainability, and (6) social cohesion (SolAbility, 2024). In principle, countries may enhance national competitiveness by fostering innovative and environmentally friendly technologies grounded in natural capital, governance efficiency, intellectual capital, and resource endowments, thereby influencing firms' environmental behavior (Oduro, 2024). In addition, Bitencourt et al. (2020) suggested that GSCI may shape firm performance because higher GSCI levels reflect a stronger orientation toward sustainable and environmental development. Following the approach of adopting the median GSCI for each country (Bitencourt et al., 2020; Oduro, 2024), two groups were formed: low and high GSCI. Based on these arguments, the hypotheses are proposed as follows:

H_{5a}: Methodological variables have a moderating effect on the relationship between GL and SP.

H_{5b}: Economic variables have a moderating effect on the relationship between GL and SP.

H_{5c}: Contextual variables have a moderating effect on the relationship between GL and SP.

This study seeks to examine the relationship between GL and SP and its subcomponents—“financial, environmental, and social.” It also aims to conduct moderator analyses to test potential moderator effects across the following domains: “methodological (industry type, sample size), economic (CD), and Contextual (FTI and GSCI).” Consistent with this purpose, the study's conceptual model is presented as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

3. METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to examine the relationship between GL and SP using a meta-analytic approach. Meta-analysis is a quantitative technique that integrates results from multiple empirical studies to produce a single pooled estimate (Şen & Yıldırım, 2020). By aggregating data across prior quantitative research, it enables a systematic synthesis of the evidence base rather than relying on findings from individual studies in isolation. Accordingly, the present analysis seeks to obtain more robust and precise conclusions by combining the results of all relevant studies on the topic into a unified summary effect (Borenstein et al., 2013). Put differently, meta-analysis entails the structured review and re-analysis of previously conducted individual studies to derive an overarching inference (Hedges, 1992).

3.1. Inclusion Criteria for Studies

The meta-analysis focused on quantitative studies examining the relationship between green logistics and sustainable performance. Eligible studies were drawn from articles published in international peer-reviewed journals and were identified through searches of the Web of Science, EBSCO Host, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases using the keywords “green logistics” and “sustainable performance” or “Economic Performance” or “Environmental Performance” or “Social Performance”. The initial search, conducted without publication-year restrictions, yielded 857 records. The inclusion process and selection criteria for the meta-analysis are presented below using a PRISMA flowchart, consistent with the guidance provided by Page et al. (2021) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. PRISMA Flowchart

Reference: (Page et al., 2021)

In developing the dataset for this research, the initial pool consisted of 857 studies identified through the search strategy. Each record was screened in line with the meta-analysis procedures, and only studies meeting the eligibility requirements were retained for analysis. As part of the exclusion process, publication types such as books, book chapters, book reviews, and editorial materials were removed because they did not allow a consistent examination of the relationships between the study variables. In addition, only studies published in English were included. Records that did not match the predefined keywords, or that lacked key information required for effect-size computation—such as sample size and either a correlation coefficient (r) or a regression coefficient (β) reflecting the relationship between the research variables—were also excluded. Following these steps, the final dataset comprised 19 studies for the meta-analysis.

3.2. Data Coding

A coding form was created in Microsoft Excel to extract key information from each study systematically included in the meta-analysis. The authors carefully designed the form to ensure comprehensive capture of relevant data during the coding process. To support the reliability of the values used to calculate effect sizes, the study followed the guidance of Cooper et al. (Cooper et al., 2019), who recommend excluding studies with relatively low publication quality to ensure that effect-size estimates are valid. Rosenthal (Rosenthal, 1979) also highlights the value of incorporating both published and unpublished studies; however, defining what constitutes a “qualified” publication is not always straightforward. For this reason, publication quality should be evaluated using established criteria, including whether the measurement scales demonstrate adequate psychometric properties—particularly validity and reliability—within individual studies (Şen & Yıldırım, 2020). In the present analysis, intercoder reliability was assessed using the Cohen's Kappa coefficient, as recommended by Cohen (1960, 2013). A Kappa value of 0.60 is considered indicative of good agreement (Şen & Yıldırım, 2020). The Cohen Kappa coefficient calculated between coders in this study was 0.92, reflecting perfect agreement.

The coding form captured the study title, authors, publication year, sample size (n), correlation coefficient (r) or regression coefficient (beta), and Cronbach's alpha values. In addition, moderator variables expected to influence the GL–SP relationship—namely, “industry type, sample size, CD, FTI, and GSCI”—were also recorded. Because the research relied on secondary data, no ethics committee approval was required for the studies included in the meta-analysis. The studies retained for meta-analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Study Information Included in the Study

GL-SP Relationship		Components						
S.N.	Studies	N	Industry	Continent/Country	Sustainable	Financial	Environmental	Social
1	(Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021)	152	Mixed	Africa	✓			✓
2	(Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020)	274	Mixed	Africa	✓		✓	✓
3	(Zhou et al., 2023)	271	Mixed	Asia	✓			
4	(Yingfei et al., 2022)	335	Service	Asia/China	✓			
5	(Verma, 2024)	215	Mixed	Asia/Oman	✓			
6	(Onyango et al., 2014)	32	Manufacturing	Africa/Kenya		✓		
7	(Trivellas et al., 2020)	134	Mixed	Europe/Greece		✓	✓	✓
8	(Wong et al., 2014)	395	Manufacturing	Asia/China	✓		✓	
9	(Ellibeş & Akçadağ, 2023)	86	Logistics	Europe/Turkey	✓			
10	(Choi & Zhang, 2011)	98	Logistics	Asia/China	✓			
11	(Baah et al., 2020)	32	Manufacturing	Africa/Ghana		✓		
12	(Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2021)	240	Mixed	Africa/Ghana	✓		✓	✓
13	(Çengel & Er, 2022)	136	Logistics	Europe/Turkey		✓	✓	✓
14	(Afum et al., 2022)	174	Logistics	Africa/Ghana	✓			
15	(Sidek et al., 2021)	387	Mixed	Asia/Malaysia	✓	✓	✓	
16	(Ellison et al., 2024)	220	Manufacturing	Africa/Ghana		✓	✓	✓
17	(Odoek et al., 2024)	300	Logistics	Africa/ Kenya	✓			
18	(Maurya et al., 2023)	176	Manufacturing	Asia/India	✓	✓	✓	
19	(Baah, 2019)	190	Logistics	Africa/Ghana	✓			

Note: Mixed Industry: Agricultural, Electronic, Drink and Food Industry, Textile Factories, Drink and Alcohol Factories, Shoe Manufacturers, Plastics and Rubber, Hotels, Movie and Music Distributors, Cinemas, Logistics sector, Transportation, Storage, Shipping brokers, Medicine, Textile, Big stores, Ready-made clothing, food, manufacturer, Construction products production, Chemical Oil and Oil Products Production, Cosmetics.

The distribution of the 19 studies included in the meta-analysis, by year, is presented more descriptively in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Changes in The Number of Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis over the Years

Figure 3 presents the trend in the number of studies investigating the relationship between GL and CP across the years. It should be noted, however, that the figure reflects only the studies included in the meta-analysis; therefore, qualitative research is not captured in this distribution. Overall, the pattern suggests that scholarly interest in these topics has intensified in recent years. Notably, the largest share of included studies was published in 2020 (4 studies), followed by a steady stream of publications in 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024 (3 studies). Accordingly, Figure 3 reports the year-by-year distribution of the 19 studies retained in the meta-analysis.

Figure 4. The Distribution of the Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis by Countries

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of studies included in the meta-analysis by country. The studies were mainly conducted in Ghana (5), China (3), Turkey (2), and Kenya (2).

3.3. Meta-Analysis Procedures

In this study, the psychometric meta-analysis approach proposed by Hunter and Schmidt (1982) was employed, and all computations and interpretations were based on correlation coefficients (Hunter, 2004). Given the nature of correlation-based evidence, the relational tests synthesized in this study also carry an implicit causal interpretation. The statistical significance of the examined relationships was evaluated using confidence intervals for effect sizes, with significance inferred when the lower and upper confidence limits did not include zero. To interpret the magnitude of correlations, this study followed the effect-size benchmarks referenced by Şen and Yıldırım (2020), which rely on Cohen's conventional thresholds for correlation-based meta-analytic effect sizes: 0.10 (small), 0.30 (medium), and 0.50 (large) (Cohen, 1960, 1992, 2013). For analysis, Pearson correlation coefficients were transformed into Fisher's z values, and the pooled estimates were then converted back to correlation coefficients to facilitate interpretation (Borenstein et al., 2021).

All analyses were conducted using sample size and correlation coefficients. Accordingly, the following statistics were considered: Fisher's Z, the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval for the correlation estimate, Cochran's Q, Tau squared (T^2), and I^2 —indices commonly reported in heterogeneity assessments in the meta-analysis literature (Borenstein et al., 2021; Cooper et al., 2019). The Q test evaluates whether the observed effect sizes across individual studies differ beyond what would be expected by sampling error alone; a significant Q statistic ($p < 0.05$) indicates meaningful between-study differences. The I^2 statistic represents the proportion of total variation attributable to real differences across studies rather than chance. When Q is non-significant, and I^2 is low (typically below 25%), the evidence suggests that effect sizes are relatively consistent across studies. Moderate heterogeneity (I^2 between 25% and 75%) implies some substantive differences, whereas high heterogeneity (I^2 greater than 75%) indicates substantial variability in effects. In addition, T^2 was used as an estimate of the variance of true effect sizes across studies (Erbiçer et al., 2024). Assessing heterogeneity is important because elevated heterogeneity may reflect the presence of two or more subgroups with systematically different underlying effects (Şen & Yıldırım, 2020). Although heterogeneity tests are often used to guide the choice between fixed-effect and random-effects models, the reporting in this study followed the random-effects model throughout, consistent with recommendations that meta-analyses should typically rely on random-effects assumptions (Field & Gillett, 2010; Hedges, 1992). In addition, average effect sizes were computed separately for each variable and each performance dimension, and both heterogeneity and publication-bias assessments were conducted.

To explore potential sources of heterogeneity, Analog ANOVA was performed for categorical moderators. At least three studies are required to conduct an Analog ANOVA (Borenstein et al., 2021); therefore, moderator analyses were limited to variables that met this criterion. The categorical moderators considered were industry type and sample size. Industry type was coded into four categories—Logistics, Manufacturing, Services, and Mixed—based on information reported in the included studies. Studies spanning more than one sector were coded as Mixed (see Table 1). Sample size was coded into two groups (small vs. large) by consulting the methodological sections of the primary studies and using the median sample size as the cut-off value. For the coding of CD, FTI, and GSCI, see Appendix A1. In addition, a coding scheme was developed to operationalize the variables (see Table A1 in the Appendix).

Publication bias was assessed using a funnel plot and, to provide more quantitative evidence, the Egger et al. (Egger, 1997) test (One-tailed p) and the Begg and Mazumdar (Begg, 1994) ranked correlation test (Kendall Tau coefficient). Non-significant results in both tests ($p > 0.05$) were interpreted as indicating no evidence of publication bias. All analyses were conducted under a random-effects model, and computations were performed using CMA 4.0 (Comprehensive Meta Analysis v4).

4. FINDINGS

4.1. Publication Bias

Figure 5 displays a funnel scatter plot illustrating the distribution of effect sizes from the individual studies included in the analysis and the potential for publication bias.

Figure 5. Funnel Plot of the Relationship between GL and SP.

After examining Figure 5, it can be observed that the individual study estimates are distributed relatively symmetrically within the funnel plot. This pattern suggests that publication bias is unlikely to be a serious concern in the dataset. Nevertheless, visual inspection of a funnel plot alone is not sufficient for a definitive assessment of publication bias. Therefore, two complementary statistical procedures were applied to provide quantitative evidence: the Egger Regression Test and the Begg and Mazumdar rank correlation test. The corresponding results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of Publication Bias

	Egger Test		Begg and Mazumdar	
	One-tailed p		Kendall Tau b	Two-tailed p
GL-SP	0,292		-0,004	0,968
GL-FP	0,398		0,000	1,000
GL-EP	0,398		-0,035	0,901
GL-Soc.P	0,323		0,400	0,259

Egger's regression test ($p > 0.05$) and Begg and Mazumdar's rank correlation test ($p > 0.05$) indicated no evidence of publication bias for the GL–SP relationship or for the analyses involving the other outcome variables “FP, EP, Soc.P.”

4.2. Meta-Analysis Main Findings

In this study, the Q test, Tau square (T^2), and I^2 values were used to evaluate heterogeneity between studies. Heterogeneity statistics (Q, T^2 and I^2) and effect size (ESr) are presented in Table 3. The studies included in the current study examine the relationships between GL-SP and other independent variables (financial, environmental, social), which appear to exhibit high heterogeneity. Additionally, T^2 showed that the variance in true effect sizes was low.

Table 3. Meta-Analysis Results

RANDOM MODEL	k	Total effect	Sample size	ESr	SE	95% CI of r		Z-value	Q-statistic	I^2 (%)	T^2
						LL	UL				
H1=>GL-SP	19	35	7528	0,469	0,052	0,386	0,544	9,815***	741,289***	95,144	0,093
H2=>GL-FP	9	9	1783	0,421	0,103	0,243	0,572	4,367***	116,530***	93,135	0,085
H3=>GL-EP	8	8	1962	0,520	0,103	0,358	0,652	5,599***	140,002***	95,000	0,080
H4=>GL-Soc.P	6	6	1156	0,353	0,124	0,125	0,546	2,975***	86,128***	94,195	0,087

Note: *** $p < 0.001$; k number of work; Cochran's Q tests of heterogeneity; SE Standard error; LL Lower Limit; UL Upper Limit; T^2 tau squared; CI confidence interval.

Average effect size (ESr) estimates the heterogeneity statistics (Q, T^2 , and I^2) under the random-effects model; these are summarized in Table 3. Looking at the results of the meta-analysis, in which the relationships between GL and SP and the subcomponents (financial, environmental, and social performance) were considered separately, the relationship between GL and SP was analyzed using 35 effect sizes. The findings were interpreted within the framework of the correlation values suggested by Cohen. The analysis results revealed a strong, significant relationship ($r=0.469$, $p=0.000$) between green logistics and sustainable performance. Based on the literature review, there is a clear relationship between GL and SP (Moczyłowska et al., 2024). Accordingly, hypothesis H1 is supported, highlighting the central role of sustainability in logistics (Khayyat et al., 2024). Overall, the findings suggest that implementing GL practices substantially improves SP, consistent with previous studies (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2021; Centobelli et al., 2018). In addition, GL practices contribute to outcomes such as waste reduction, cost minimization, and broader improvements in SP (Odock et al., 2024). The adoption of GL is further supported by its potential to lower costs, increase recovery rates, and strengthen the sustainable performance of firms pursuing sustainable development and competitive advantage (Wang, 2019).

The relationship between GL and FP was also examined using nine effect sizes. The results indicate a strong and significant association ($r=0.421$, $p<0.000$). The literature similarly suggests that GL practices reduce environmental harm and operational costs related to the production of goods and services, conserve energy, and improve competitive dynamics, thereby supporting financial performance (Lai & Wong, 2012). Thus, the evidence supports the GL–FP relationship, and hypothesis H2 is accepted. Although initial investments in GL may represent a short-term challenge, these practices can generate long-term savings and improved FP by reducing operating costs (Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum & Ahenkorah, 2020; Agyabeng-Mensah, Ahenkorah, et al., 2020; Chatzoudes et al., 2024).

For environmental performance, the GL–EP association was estimated from eight effect sizes. The pooled effect indicates a strong and statistically significant relationship between GL and EP ($r=0.520$, $p<0.001$), consistent with prior research. Therefore, hypothesis H3 is accepted. Existing studies indicate that GL can strengthen an organization's environmentally responsible reputation, enhance the effectiveness of

environmental management, and improve overall EP (Khayyat et al., 2024). In line with this view, organizations adopting GL practices tend to report higher levels of EP (Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020; Agyabeng-Mensah, Ahenkorah, et al., 2020; Karia, 2020). These results reinforce the need for logistics firms to intensify environmental initiatives by expanding the adoption of GL practices (Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023).

Finally, the relationship between GL and Soc. P. was examined using six effect sizes. The results reveal a robust and significant association between GL and Soc. P. ($r=0.353$, $p=0.000$). Accordingly, hypothesis H4 is accepted, and the evidence is consistent with the literature. GL adoption strengthens corporate reputation (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2023; Baah et al., 2020). More broadly, GL practices appear to positively affect multiple dimensions of performance, including operational efficiency, financial outcomes, and social reputation (Sharma et al., 2023). Firms that implement GL may also be better positioned to attract informed customers and investors, thereby further enhancing their social reputation (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2021; Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021).

4.3. Moderator Analyses

In this study, moderator analyses were conducted to examine whether a third variable could influence the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The results indicated that the relationships between GL–SP and the other independent variables exhibited heterogeneity (see Table 3). Accordingly, subgroup analyses were carried out in line with the criteria proposed by Borenstein et al. (2021). Differences across moderator subcategories were tested using Analog-ANOVA, and the corresponding results are reported in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Moderator Analysis Results (for SP and FP)

Moderators/ Categories	GL-SP					GL-FP				
	k	Sample size	ESr	95% CIr	Q-between	k	Sample size	ESr	95% CIr	Q-between
<i>Methodological Effect</i>										
<i>Industrial Type</i>										
Logistics	8	1256	0,595***	0,410	0,733	1	136	0,301	0,506	0,715
Manufacturing	10	2042	0,463***	0,287	0,610	4	460	0,473**	0,154	0,702
Mixed	16	4303	0,400***	0,294	0,497	4	947	0,311*	0,038	0,540
Service	1	335	0,800***	0,759	0,836	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Sample size</i>										
Large	18	5548	0,524***	0,501	0,615	3	881	0,483*	0,070	0,754
Small	17	2214	0,430***	0,291	0,551	6	662	0,385***	0,238	0,515
<i>Contextual Effect</i>										
<i>Frontier Technologies Index (FTI)</i>										
Hight	7	2384	0,578***	0,486	0,640	1	387	0,507***	0,452	0,554
LM	16	3208	0,379***	0,245	0,483	5	710	0,364*	0,025	0,573
LOW	1	271	0,447***	0,366	0,513	-	-	-	-	-
UM	13	2073	0,402***	0,284	0,496	3	446	0,402***	0,191	0,547
<i>Global Sustainable Competition Index (GSCI)</i>										
LOW	22	4522	0,374***	0,266	0,464	6	886	0,354**	0,092	0,533
High	15	3414	0,513***	0,439	0,572	3	657	0,470***	0,325	0,572
<i>Economic Effect</i>										
<i>Country Development</i>										
Low Income	25	3994	0,393***	0,304	0,469	7	844	0,382***	0,177	0,527
High Income	12	2253	0,516***	0,408	0,593	2	699	0,447**	0,122	0,621

Note: * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; *** $p<0.001$; k number of effect sizes; Cochran's Q tests of heterogeneity; CI confidence interval.

Moderator analyses indicated that industry type (logistics, manufacturing, services, and mixed) significantly moderated both the GL–SP relationship ($Q_B=74.219$, $p<0.001$) and the GL–FP relationship ($Q_B=6.115$, $p<0.05$). By contrast, sample size (Greater Than The Average, Otherwise) did not emerge as a significant moderator for either GL–SP ($Q_B=1.294$, $p>0.05$) or GL–FP ($Q_B=0.239$, $p>0.05$). On this basis, H5a was supported. Regarding contextual indicators, the FTI (High LM, Low UM) moderated the GL–SP relationship ($Q_B=9.040$, $p<0.05$), but did not significantly moderate GL–FP ($Q_B=2.636$, $p>0.05$). Similarly, the GSCI (Low, High) showed a significant moderating effect on GL–SP ($Q_B=5.450$, $p<0.05$), whereas it was not a significant moderator for GL–FP ($Q_B=0.883$, $p>0.05$). Accordingly, H5b was supported. Finally, CD (Low Income, High Income) also moderated the GL–SP relationship ($Q_B=3.386$, $p<0.05$). However, it did not significantly moderate the GL–FP relationship ($Q_B=0.163$, $p>0.05$) and was therefore not considered a moderator in that model. Consequently, H5c was partially supported.

Table 5. Moderator Analysis Results (for EP and SocP)

Moderators/ Categories		GL-EP					GL-SocP				
	k	Sample size	ESr	95% CIr	Q-between	k	Sample size	ESr	95% CIr	Q-between	
Methodological Effect											
<i>Industrial Type</i>											
Logistics	1	136	0,677***	0,574	0,759		1	136	0,310***	0,149	0,454
Manufacturing	3	791	0,473*	0,050	0,752	3,596	1	220	0,697***	0,623	0,759
Mixed	4	1035	0,510***	0,297	0,675		4	800	0,245**	0,091	0,388
<i>Sample size</i>											
Large	5	1506	0,566***	0,399	0,696		4	422	0,348	0,110	0,685
Small	3	446	0,434*	0,013	0,737	0,428	3	734	0,351***	0,275	0,422
Contextual Effect											
<i>Frontier Technologies Index (FTI)</i>											
Hight	2	782	0,491***	0,451	0,527		-	-	-	-	-
LM	3	734	0,526**	0,226	0,665	0,400	4	886	0,338*	0,011	0,550
UM	3	446	0,409*	-0,014	0,627		2	270	0,344***	0,243	0,429
<i>Global Sustainable Competition Index (GSCI)</i>											
LOW	4	910	0,437*	0,074	0,626		4	886	0,338*	0,011	0,550
Hight	4	1052	0,509***	0,456	0,553	0,316	2	270	0,344***	0,243	0,429
Economic Effect											
<i>Country Development</i>											
Low Income	5	910	0,451***	0,207	0,598		4	886	0,338*	0,011	0,550
High Income	3	1052	0,515***	0,429	0,580	0,418	2	270	0,344***	0,243	0,429

Note: *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001; k number of effect sizes; Cochran’s Q tests of heterogeneity; CI confidence interval.

It was concluded that industry type was not a moderator in the relationship between GL and EP (Q_B=3.596, p>0.05). However, it was statistically significant and a moderator of the relationship between GL and SocP (Q_B = 41.761, p < 0.001). Moreover, it was concluded that sample size, FTI, GSCI, and CD did not moderate the relationship between GL-EP or GL-Soc.P.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study comprehensively examined the relationship between GL and SP using meta-analysis methods. By synthesizing empirical findings from the existing literature, the meta-analysis produced a more generalizable and accurate estimate of the GL–SP effect size, enabling more robust conclusions. The study also examined GL’s relationships with the subcomponents of SP—financial performance (FP), ecological performance (EP), and social performance (Soc.P.)—and assessed moderating influences. The analysis was based on 7,528 respondents from 19 independent studies, incorporating 35 effect sizes. Publication bias was evaluated using the funnel plot, the Egger Regression Test, and the Begg and Mazumdar ordinal correlation test; the results indicated no evidence of publication bias. Effect sizes were converted to Fisher z values for analysis and then reconverted to correlation coefficients for interpretation. All analyses were conducted under a random-effects model. The results showed a strong and statistically significant relationship between GL and SP (r=0.469, p<0.001), consistent with prior evidence (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021; Centobelli et al., 2018; Karia, 2020; Khayyat et al., 2024; Moczyłowska et al., 2024; Wang, 2019). Strong positive correlations were also observed between GL and FP (r=0.421, p<0.001), GL and EP (r=0.520, p<0.001), and GL and Soc.P. (r=0.353, p=0.000). These results align with previous studies (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2021; Agyabeng-Mensah, Afum, & Ahenkorah, 2020; Agyabeng-Mensah, Ahenkorah, et al., 2020; Baah, 2019; Baah et al., 2021; Chatzoudes et al., 2024; Khayyat et al., 2024; Odock et al., 2024; Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023).

These findings provide theoretical insights within the NRBT perspective, which emphasizes how organizations translate natural resources and environmental capabilities into sustainability outcomes and performance advantages. NRBT highlights that organizations can obtain sustainable competitive advantages through environmental resources and competencies (Barney, 1991; Hart, 1995). In this context, the present study contributes to the literature by consolidating evidence on how GL supports sustainable performance and by clarifying the role of natural resource-based competitive advantages in shaping GL’s performance implications. Specifically, the results suggest that GL enables organizations to pursue strategic goals by more efficiently deploying environmental resources and capabilities, thereby strengthening natural resource-based competitive advantage over time (Teece et al., 1997). This interpretation is consistent with the logic emphasized by Hart (1995) and parallels findings discussed by Russo & Fouts (Russo et al., 2015).

Beyond the direct effects, the moderator evidence adds nuance to NRBT explanations of sustainability strategies. The moderating effect patterns suggest that GL can impose higher financial burdens initially but yield increasing sustainability benefits over time—consistent with the argument that strategic and environmental improvements can accumulate as organizations learn, adapt, and optimize resource deployment (Wernerfelt, 1995). This pattern is also consistent with prior work indicating that GL may create short-term financial pressure while contributing to long-term sustainable development and competitive advantage (Chatzoudes et al., 2024; Khayyat et al., 2024; Odock et al., 2024). Moderator analyses further indicated that Industrial Type, FTI, GSCI, and CD the GL–SP relationship, whereas sample size does not. Identifying these contingencies extends the sustainability literature by showing that GL's effectiveness is sensitive to industry structure and broader contextual conditions.

In a business environment shaped by globalization and industrialization, adopting ecological sustainability has become increasingly imperative (Zhou et al., 2022). As trade and consumption expand, logistics activities also contribute substantially to environmental degradation (Odock et al., 2024), and evidence on climate change further reinforces the environmental relevance of logistics operations (Wang et al., 2022). From a practical perspective, integrating environmental sustainability strategies into operational processes can reduce pressure on natural resources while supporting competitive positioning (Alnaser et al., 2024; Barney, 1991). GL practices, in particular, can reduce environmental impacts and support sustainable competitive advantage through stronger corporate image and legitimacy (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2023; Baah et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2023), consistent with NRBT's emphasis on conserving valuable resources and using them efficiently (Teece et al., 1997). GL-related initiatives can also drive improvements in environmental indicators such as pollution and CO₂ emissions when embedded into operational frameworks (Khayyat et al., 2024; Luu et al., 2023; Noorliza, 2023). The observed link between natural resources and sustainable business performance suggests that environmentally oriented strategies can lower operating costs and support sustainable development (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2021; Centobelli et al., 2018), enabling improved financial and environmental outcomes with lower environmental impacts through stronger organizational competencies in resource use (Odock et al., 2024; Wang, 2019). GL can therefore reduce pressure on natural resources, improve operational processes, and facilitate the achievement of sustainability goals (Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023). In addition, the moderator findings imply that wider adoption of frontier technologies may help reduce CO₂ emissions and strengthen sustainable competitive advantage, thereby supporting sustainable performance. Similarly, the GSCI-related evidence suggests that policymakers and managers can strengthen national competitiveness by promoting innovative, environmentally friendly technologies grounded in natural capital, governance efficiency, intellectual capital, and resources, thereby shaping firms' environmental behaviors (Bitencourt et al., 2020; Oduro, 2024). Moreover, prior evidence indicates that GL improves both sustainable performance and environmental performance (Karia, 2020; Luu et al., 2023). Accordingly, firms can gain meaningful advantages by adopting ecological sustainability strategies that support environmental performance and long-term strategic goals.

Importantly, the industry-type moderation carries actionable implications for managers, indicating that GL should be operationalized differently across logistics and manufacturing contexts. In logistics-intensive settings, where environmental burdens are concentrated in transportation, warehousing, routing, and packaging (Odock et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022), managers can translate GL into measurable sustainability gains by prioritizing fuel- and route-optimization, load consolidation, reverse logistics, low-emission fleet transitions, and green warehousing practices, supported by data-driven monitoring of emissions and energy use (Khayyat et al., 2024; Luu et al., 2023; Noorliza, 2023). Because logistics operations are highly networked and interdependent, implementation is likely to be strengthened through supplier and carrier coordination, sustainability criteria in partner selection, and shared performance dashboards that align environmental targets with service-level requirements (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2023). By contrast, in manufacturing contexts—where sustainability impacts are more tightly linked to production technologies, material inputs, and process efficiency—GL can be converted into stronger FP and EP outcomes by investing in cleaner production, eco-design, waste and defect reduction, energy-efficient equipment, and closed-loop material systems, while embedding environmental objectives into continuous improvement routines and quality-management infrastructures (Centobelli et al., 2018; Karia, 2020; Van Vo & Nguyen, 2023; Wang, 2019). Across both industries, these differentiated pathways are consistent with NRBT's central claim that firms accrue sustained advantages by developing context-specific environmental capabilities and deploying natural resources more efficiently (Barney, 1991; Hart, 1995; Teece et al., 1997).

This study also has limitations associated with meta-analysis. First, the scope was constrained by missing statistical information in some primary studies—particularly the absence of correlation coefficients or standardized regression coefficients (beta values)—which may have led to the exclusion of potentially relevant evidence and may influence generalizability. Relatedly, the meta-analytic evidence base remained relatively small ($k = 19$), largely because a substantial number of otherwise eligible studies did not report effect-size information in a form that could be harmonized and synthesized. Second, the analysis included only international studies published in English, which may limit transferability across different geographic and cultural contexts. Future research should incorporate studies in additional languages and regions to better capture contextual diversity, particularly across developing economies (Hart, 1995), and to clarify how local institutional and cultural conditions affect the effectiveness of sustainable strategies. Because this study synthesized quantitative evidence, qualitative research is recommended to deepen understanding of how organizations implement GL and how natural resources and environmental capabilities are transformed into performance outcomes. Case studies, in-depth interviews, and field research could illuminate implementation barriers, organizational learning processes, and the conditions under which GL yields stronger sustainability benefits. Future work can further strengthen the NRBT-based explanation by examining how resource management and environmental sustainability strategies generate competitive advantage across contexts.

APPENDIX A

Table A1: Coding Scheme

Moderator variables were coded into three categories: methodological effect, economic effect, and contextual effect (see Table 1 for details).				
No.		Variables	Codes	Definition & examples
1.	Methodological Effect	Industry Type	Manufacturing	The article was coded as mentioned.
			Logistics	The article was coded as mentioned.
			Mixed	Logistics, manufacturing, service, etc. Articles or more sectors (Table 1 see)
			Service	The article was coded as mentioned.
		Sample size	0,1	The studies were divided into two groups: small and large. We accessed the methodological sections of each study and used the median sample size as the cut-off point (Bitencourt et al., 2020). 0=small, 1=large.
2.	Economic Effect	Country Development	Low Income High Income	A country's level of economic development is coded as low income or high income; to clarify the economic divide, World Bank data are used to classify countries as developed or developing (World Bank).
3.	Contextual Effect	Frontier Technologies Index (FTI)	HIGH	The Frontier Technology Index was calculated using the methodology presented in the Technology and Innovation Report 2021. The index provided results for 166 economies. Country rankings are arranged in four 25-point scales: low, lower-middle, upper-middle, and high (UNCTAD, 2023).
			UM	
LM				
LOW				
		Global Sustainable Competition Index (GSCI)	0,1	The Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index (GACI) from SolAbility measures countries' competitiveness in an integrated way, using 111 indicators grouped into five sub-indices: natural capital, resource efficiency and intensity, intellectual capital, governance efficiency, and social cohesion. We used the median GSCI for each country to identify the two groups: low and high GSCI levels (SolAbility, 0=LOW, 1=HIGHT).
4.		Sustainable Performance	SP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Performance is based on “financial, environmental, and social” scales. SP refers to a company's ability to achieve its organizational goals while minimizing its environmental impact (Singh & Dhir, 2019).
		Financial Performance	FP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial performance highlights the impacts of corporate activities on the economic system (Riggs et al., 2024).
		Environmental Performance	EP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental performance refers to the company's impact on the environment, including its carbon footprint, energy consumption, waste management, and natural resource use (Chuang & Huang, 2018).
		Social Performance	SocP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social performance takes into account elements related to the well-being of stakeholders, such as the health and safety of workers, the creation of employment opportunities for the surrounding community, education and training, and the reduction of risks to the general public (Das et al., 2023).
5.		Green Logistics	GL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green Logistics scale has been used, which emphasizes environmental and social responsibility with various practices that can address environmental issues (Khayyat et al., 2024). Production, distribution, packaging, product and waste management, energy- and fuel-efficient transportation, carbon emission assessment, route optimization, and reverse logistics are some of the green logistics techniques (McKinnon et al., 2015; McKinnon, 2010; Molina-Besch & Pålsson, 2014). In general, green logistics operations are considered to have a significant impact on each element of sustainable performance separately.

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